

Hawala on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the mapping of research topics around the Hawala in Islamic Financial Inclusion with a mix-method approach, namely VOSviewer bibliometric studies and library researches. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications surrounding the Hawala; (2) mapping the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization results about the Hawala based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) Mapping Research Topics around the Hawala using a Library Research. The research results show that: (1) based on mapping the distribution of journal publications, there are 32 journal publications about the Hawala; (2) based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results surrounding the Hawala are divided into 3 clusters and 46 topic items; (3) based on mapping library research studies, there are 10 The main topic revolves around the Hawala. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics surrounding the Hawala, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research surrounding the Hawala. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics surrounding the Hawala which are often or rarely studied by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Keywords: Hawala; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Inclusion

Introduction

Islamic Financial Inclusion is an industry that upholds Islamic economic rules. There are two main activities carried out by the Islamic banking Financial Inclusion party, namely channeling funds and collecting funds from the community. Distribution of funds in financing in sharia banking carries a large risk. The greater the risk experienced by sharia financial banking, the more cases that occur in that finance. One of the products in Islamic Financial Inclusion is Hawala. Hawala is the transfer of debt from the person who owes it to another party who is obliged to bear it. In the contract concept, there is a transfer of collateral or rights from one person to another. The legal basis for implementing the Hawala is the Al- Qur'an, Hadith, Ijmak, and Qiyas.

Basic Islamic Financial Inclusion Hawalas are applied in two forms of products, namely bai' al-istishana and bai' al-salam. Things that support the development of the basics of Hawalas in sharia banking provide positive performance for leaders, staff and employees to have the ability to be honest and trustworthy to serve the community. Meanwhile, the obstacles to the Hawala are the lack of socialization of the Hawala to the public and not yet optimizing the network system service facilities between online banks and the sharia banking network. Islamic Financial Inclusion must apply sharia

principles in the Hawala. According to Law Number 21 of 2008 article 19 paragraph (1) which states that "the business activities of Sharia Commercial Banks include taking over debts based on Hawalas or other contracts that do not conflict with sharia principles". That in connection with this, sharia banking is required to implement sharia principles that do not only focus on profits.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around the Hawala card on Islamic Financial Inclusion in Indonesia by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics surrounding the Hawala card, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research surrounding the Hawala card. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around the Hawala card which are often or rarely studied by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

The Hawala is the transfer of debt from one person to another with the same level of debt. Where (muhil) is a person who is both in debt and receivable, namely (muhal) is a person who is in debt to the muhil, (muhal 'alaihi) is a person who is in debt to the muhil and is obliged to pay the debt to the muhal. Fatwa on Hawala stipulates that the parties must make an agreement and a statement of consent and qabul to express their willingness to enter into a contract. According to the Fatwa issued by the National Sharia Council, Indonesian Ulema Council, namely Fatwa Number 12/DSN/-MUI/IV/2000.

Bibliometric studies are a type of research that uses quantitative methods to examine the production of scientific literature. Using this approach, one can assess the impact of field research over time to infer correlations of influence to influence, participation and association in the published literature. VOSviewer is useful software for building and visualizing bibliometric networks. Such networks can include journals, researchers, or publications, individuals, and can be built on existing theory, bibliographic incorporation, citations, or related writing. This discusses the functions of VOSviewer related to network use of this technology.

study is a method used to collect data or sources related to the topic raised in an analysis. Literature studies can be obtained from various sources such as journals, books, documentation, internet and libraries, and other meaningful sources.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research studies. The object of the research is the Hawala. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about the Hawala agreement on Islamic Financial Inclusion.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley

Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Hawala " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications surrounding the Hawala using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around the Hawala using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) Mapping Research Topics around the Hawala using a Library Research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Hawalah Contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion

There are 32 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2010 to 2022. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Scientific publication data about Akad Hawala by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2010	1	2014	1	2019	3
2011	1	2015	1	2020	5
2012	1	2016	1	2021	8
2013	1	2018	2	2022	5
Total 32					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there is 1 publishing industry that publishes the most journals regarding the Hawala Agreement, namely: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, with a total of 2 journal articles. Meanwhile, other journal publishers only publish 1 journal article.

Table 2. Affiliate/Industry data for research publishers

Affiliate/Industry Name	Number of Publications
Journal of Islamic Economics and Business	2

Adzkiya: Journal of Sharia Law and Economics, Al-Mizan, Al-Mustashfa: Research Journal of Sharia Economic Law, Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences, Immanence: Journal of Islamic Economics, Management and Accounting, Indonesian Interdisciplinary Journal of Sharia Economics (IIJSE), IQTISHADUNA: Our Economic Scientific Journal, Jatiswara, Journal of Indonesian Comparative of Sharia Law, Juripol (Journal of the Medan Ganesha Polytechnic Institution), Jurisdiction: Journal of Law and Sharia, Journal of Sharia Economics, Journal Istiqro, Journal of Management, Economics, Finance and Accounting, Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Legal Media Journal, PROFIT JOURNAL, Islamic Family Law Research Journal, Sentris Journal, MAQASIDI: Journal of Sharia and Law, Legal Issues, MASLAHAH (Journal of Islamic Law and Sharia Banking), MUAMALATUNA, Muqtasid: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Nobel Management Review, Qawanin: Journal of Economic Sharia Law, Reslaj : Religion Education Social Laa Roiba Journal, Syntax Idea, TAFATQUH: Journal of Economic Law Sharia and Ahwal Syahsiyah, Ushuluna: Journal of Ushuluddin Science.

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Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Mapping Research Topics Regarding the Hawala on Islamic Financial Inclusion using the VOSviewer Bibliometric Study

Search results on the Garuda website (Digital Referral Garba) regarding Akad Hawala research articles are downloaded in RIS (Research Information Systems) format then input and analyzed using the VOSViewer device. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development map regarding the Hawala Agreement

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Based on the results of the analysis, this research is divided into 3 clusters with 46 topics. Following are the results of the analysis :

- Cluster 1 consisting of 24 topics, namely : activity, al Hawala, article, bad debt, bank, condition, data, debt, etc. mui iv, fund, Hawala, Hawala, Islamic banking, Islamic finance company, kafalah, credit, Islamic Financial Inclusion, muhal alaih, muhil, position, sharia, tabarru, transfer, wakalah.
- Cluster 2 consists of 16 topics, namely: bailout, bank Indonesia, bank Indonesia circular, concept, etc. mui, fatwa, Hawala, idea, Hawala in circulars, Hawala muqayyadah, Hawala idea, object, qardh, sharia factoring, type, wakalah bil ujarah.
- Cluster 3 consists of 6 topics, namely: debt transfer, differences, Hawala system, Indonesia, paper, system.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Implementation of the Hawala on Terrorism Crimes, Money Laundering and Abuse in Other Crimes

There are 23 studies on this topic. The research approaches and methods used are: a qualitative approach with explanatory normative research methods. Data collection methods used include: library research, field research and interviews.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) This transaction is very likely to occur in the financing of international scale terrorist crimes. This is because these transactions can be carried out at a relatively faster time than the remittance system / transfer service carried out by banks.
- (b) Knowledge of how money works with this contract can prevent acts of terrorism. In Indonesia, this is specifically handled by the Indonesian

National Police (Densus 88 Anti-Terror) and the Financial Transaction Reports and Analysis Center (PPATK).

- (c) Following current technological developments, the concept of the Hawala in crypto transactions has become an alternative for fundraising or crowdfunding by global terrorist networks. They diversify their financial portfolio through cryptocurrencies to maintain their operations and survival.
- (d) One method of money laundering is placement. This is the placement of large amounts of money which are the proceeds of crime, such as corruption, then broken down into small amounts, and placed in the banking financial system, both on a national and international/global scale.
- (e) The application of the Hawala Agreement in the context of criminal acts of terrorism, money laundering and abuse in crimes is not common or common. The Hawala is an Islamic legal concept relating to the transfer of debt responsibility between two parties, which is often used in the context of financial and business transactions. However, this concept is not directly relevant to criminal acts of terrorism, money laundering or other crimes. The crime of terrorism is an act of violence that aims to create fear among the public and influence government policy. This involves illegal activities that violate criminal law and national security. Money laundering, on the other hand, involves converting criminal proceeds into assets that appear legal to the naked eye. Meanwhile, misuse in crime refers to the use of assets or resources in an unlawful manner for personal or group gain. In handling criminal acts of terrorism, money laundering and criminal abuse, the laws and regulations applicable in each country are usually the main reference. The national legal system regulates the investigation, prosecution and punishment of perpetrators of these crimes based on existing laws. In general, law enforcement uses an approach that involves cooperation between various government agencies, such as the police, intelligence agencies, financial authorities, and the courts. They conduct investigations, monitoring, and analysis of financial activities that are suspicious or related to the crime. In some cases, the flow of funds or financial transactions related to criminal acts of terrorism, money laundering, or criminal abuse may involve money transfers through banking systems or financial networks. In this regard, financial authorities often cooperate with banks and financial institutions to track and block suspicious transactions and report them to the competent authorities. In the context of Islamic law, there are other concepts related to financial crimes such as riba (interest), maysir (gambling), and gharar (uncertainty). These principles are used in Islamic financial law to prevent financial practices that are detrimental to society. However, implementation varies depending on the jurisdiction and country implementing sharia law.

Mapping Research Topics using a Library Research around the Implementation of the Hawala on Islamic Financial Inclusion

There are 11 studies on this topic. The research approaches and methods used are: first, a qualitative approach using descriptive library research methods obtained from books, classical scholarly books and journals; and

second, library research. The data analysis techniques used are data reduction and presentation, as well as drawing conclusions.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) The use of Hawalas is still small/minimal in Islamic Financial Inclusion. In fact, in the list of products and services in sharia banking, none of them use the Hawala.
- (b) The Hawala, whose original law was a tabarru' contract / please help, then in Islamic Financial Inclusion is transformed into a mu'awadhat / business / profit-seeking contract or into a Hawala bil Ujrah contract.
- (c) The implementation of the Hawala in Islamic Financial Inclusion includes: factoring, post-dated checks, bill discounting and e-commerce transactions.
- (d) the Bai' Al-Istishna' product in Islamic Financial Inclusion. This is supported by good performance, good commitment, tough managerial and honest mentality of all sharia bank staff. Meanwhile, the obstacles include weak literacy in public understanding of Bai' Al-Istishna' products resulting from Hawalas at sharia banks.
- (e) The following are the general steps in implementing a Hawala in Islamic Financial Inclusion: (1) Identification of the parties involved: The party who wishes to transfer ownership rights or responsibility for assets or liabilities must identify the parties involved in the transaction, namely penghawil (transfer of rights) and mahwala (party who receives rights). (2) Agreement on terms: The hawil and mahwala need to agree on the terms of the transfer of rights in writing. These terms include the amount of assets or liabilities to be transferred, the time period, and other relevant conditions. (3) Transfer of rights: After an agreement on the terms is reached, the hawil legally transfers ownership rights or responsibility for assets or liabilities to the mahwala. This transfer can be done through a written or symbolic statement. (4) Acceptance and acceptance of responsibilities: Mahwala must expressly accept the transfer of rights and responsibilities given by the hawil. This acceptance can be done by signature or other written statement. (5) The hawil is free from responsibility: After the transfer of rights, the hawil becomes free from responsibility for the assets or liabilities that have been transferred to the mahwala. Mahwala becomes the owner or is fully responsible for these assets or liabilities.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Implementation of the Hawala on Problem Financing

There are 2 studies on this topic. The approach and research methods used are: a qualitative approach with library research methods obtained from books and journals. The research objects include: KJKS UGT BMT Sidogiri KCP Omben.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) One alternative to reduce problematic financing in Islamic Financial Inclusion is the Hawala. This provides an advantage for debtors to settle their debts with creditors.
- (b) There is bailout funding to provide gifts to those who are blessed and become a source of non-financial income/ fee based income for Islamic Financial Inclusion.

- (c) In practice, between muhil and muhal 'alih go to Islamic Financial Inclusion, then complete the administrative requirements. And no coercion is permitted between the muhil and muhal 'alaih parties in this transaction.
- (d) The existence of binding conditions for Islamic Financial Inclusion aims to prevent customers from committing fraud, negligence, breaking promises (default) or violating mutually agreed agreements.
- (e) The following are several steps that can be taken in implementing the Hawala Agreement in problematic financing: (1) Identification of problematic financing: Identification of problematic financing is carried out by evaluating creditors who have difficult debts or are unable to pay. This could happen due to financial problems, an unprofitable business, or other factors. (2) Establish a Hawala agreement: Once problematic financing is identified, the next step is to establish a Hawala agreement between the creditor who owns the debt and the party who will take over the debt. This agreement can involve various aspects, such as the amount of debt to be transferred, the period for transferring the debt, and other terms. (3) Acceptance of the party taking over the debt: The party taking over the debt must agree to accept the debt. They must understand the consequences and risks associated with such problematic financing. (4) Debt payment and settlement: After the Hawala agreement is established, the party who takes over the debt will become the new creditor. This party is responsible for collecting and settling the debt. They can determine the payment method agreed upon with the original creditor. (5) Monitoring and evaluation: During the process of implementing the Hawala Agreement, it is important to monitor and evaluate the progress of debt payments. This aims to ensure that the debt is resolved properly and the party taking over the debt acts in accordance with the agreed agreement.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Implementation of Take Over Transaction Agreements

There are 2 studies on this topic. The research approaches and methods used are: (a) qualitative approach using library research methods obtained from books and journals; (b) descriptive method obtained from field observations and interviews. One of the research objects is Bank Jabar Banten Syariah Pandeglang.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) The use of the Hawala in this transaction is a fairly complicated contract model and the most difficult to implement in sharia banking. There is a non-compliance with sharia principles and transactions, even though it is based on the DSN-MUI fatwa.
- (b) The implications of the Hawala in this transaction give rise to complex accounting treatment and there are no standards governing the finances of this contract.
- (c) a hybrid contract arising in the implementation of this contract. This makes it difficult for perpetrators of these transactions to be free from deception (hilah) regarding sharia compliance.
- (d) There is a situation that often occurs in the practice of Hawalas in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely regarding the transfer of debt without the

knowledge of the party or in this case the sharia bank as a third party/ muhal 'alaih. Cases like this are called fraudulent transfers.

- (e) The following are several general stages in implementing the Hawala for a take over transaction: (1) Identification of the Company to be Taken Over: The initial stage in the take over transaction is identifying the company to be taken over. Usually, the company to be taken over has certain criteria and characteristics that are desired by interested parties. (2) Research and Evaluation: Parties interested in carrying out a take over transaction will carry out research and evaluation of the company to be taken over. This research includes analysis of financials, assets, operational performance, markets, and other relevant factors. The results of this research will be used as a basis for determining the value of the company to be taken over. (3) Negotiations and Offers: After research and evaluation have been carried out, interested parties will begin the negotiation process with the owner or controller of the company to be taken over. Interested parties will offer prices and terms of offer to parties who have power in the company to be taken over. (4) Contract Completion: If the party having power agrees with the offer, then both parties will complete the acquisition contract or take over agreement. This contract will include details regarding price, payment methods, repayment schedule, and other terms related to the transfer of ownership. (5) Implementation of Payment and Transfer of Ownership: After the contract is signed, the party carrying out the take over will make payments according to the agreement reached. After payment is made, the transfer of company ownership will be carried out officially in accordance with the applicable laws of the country concerned. (6) Integration Process: After the take over transaction is completed, the taking over party will begin the integration process of the newly acquired company. This process involves merging the acquired company's operations, human resources, systems, and procedures into the acquiring company.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Implementation of the Hawala Agreement in Multiservice Financing

There are 2 studies on this topic. The research approaches and methods used are: first, a qualitative approach using library research methods obtained from books and journals; and second, field research through interviews, where the object of research is the community.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) The use of the Hawala as an alternative to multi-service financing is believed to be easier, more innovative and competitive than the use of other contracts, such as kafalah and ijarah.
- (b) There are two alternatives in multiservice financing with a Hawala, namely using a Hawala alone and combining two or more contracts in one transaction agreement. Even though this second alternative is prohibited by some ulama, the majority of jurists allow it because it is in accordance with the maqashid of sharia and in its implementation it must not go outside the boundaries and corridors of sharia.
- (c) The mechanism for buying and selling motorbike credit at a dealer can use the Hawala Muqayyadah bi Al-Dain contract.

- (d) In the context of multiservice financing, the Hawala can be implemented in the following way: (1) Identification of the parties involved: The first party is the party who needs financing (muwahhil), the second party is the party providing the financing (muwahhal), and the third party is the party who receive financing (mustawih). (2) Determination of the amount and terms of financing: The first party and the second party agree on the amount of financing to be provided, as well as the conditions relating to the financing, such as the term, profit level and payment obligations. (3) Mustawih approval: The third party (mustawih) must give approval to the transfer of debt or payment responsibility made through this Hawala. (4) Implementation of the Hawala: After obtaining approval from the third party, the first party transfers the debt or payment responsibility to the second party. The second party then becomes the party responsible for paying off the debt or making payments to the third party in accordance with the agreed terms. (5) Repayment and settlement of financing: The second party will pay off the debt or make payments to the third party in accordance with the agreement stipulated in the Hawala.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Juridical Studies on the Hawala

There are 6 studies on this topic. The approaches, methods and research techniques used are: first, normative juridical based on primary, secondary and tertiary legal data; second, the statutory and conceptual approach; and third, search techniques through literature study by taking an inventory of statutory regulations, literature books, journals and lecture materials.

The research findings on this problem are:

- (a) DSN-MUI Fatwa No. 12/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning Hawala, No. 31/DSN-MUI/VI/2002 concerning debt transfer and No. 58/DSN-MUI/V/2007 concerning Hawala bil Ujrah;
- (b) The Hawala Agreement is contained in Article 1 numbers 20 and 21 POJK No. 31/POJK.05/2014;
- (c) The technical implementation of the Hawala in sharia banking is contained in Bank Indonesia Circular Letter (SEBI) No. 10/14/DPbS dated 17 March 2008.
- (d) Compilation of Islamic Economic Law (KHES) Articles 318-328.
- (e) The differences in the concept of factoring according to the DSN-MUI fatwa and Bank Indonesia Circular Letter (SEBI) relate to the implementing industry, dispute resolution industry, processing of receivables, transaction objects, funding and the existence of ujrah / wages.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Hawala according to the Koran and Hadith

There are 2 studies on this topic. The approach and research methods used are: a qualitative approach with descriptive library research methods obtained from books and journals.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) The Hawala is defined as the fulfillment of promises implied in debts. The Koran explains that fulfilling promises is a Muslim's obligation that he must fulfill, as Allah Ta'ala says in Surah Al-Isra' verse 34: "... and Fulfill

your promises, because you will definitely be held accountable for those promises."

- (b) The Hawala is about helping each other in virtue, accompanied by piety. Allah Ta'ala says in Surah Al-Maidah verse 2: "... and help you in (doing) virtue and piety, and do not help in committing sins and transgressions. And fear Allah, verily Allah is very severe in punishment."
- (c) The Hawala was permitted by Rasulullah Sallallahu 'Alaihi Wasallam in his words narrated by Al-Hasan and Qatadah in the book of Sahih Bukhari: "... it is permissible for two people who are sharing to divide their share into several parts, some will get a share in the form of goods and some will get a share in the form of receivables. If the debt is not paid, then the person who received the share of the receivable is not allowed to ask for his or her share. "

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Hawala according to Muamalah Fiqh and Fiqhiyyah Rules

There are 6 studies on this topic. The approach and research methods used are: a qualitative approach with descriptive library research methods obtained from books and journals.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) There are 7 important elements in the Hawala, namely: first, the definition of the Hawala according to the jurists, including: Hanafiyyah, Al-Jazairiy, Syihab Al-Din Al-Qalyubiy, Muhammad Syata Al-Dimyathiy, Ibrahim Al-Bajuriy, Taqiyuddin, Sayyid Sabiq and Idris Ahmad. Second, the legal basis of the Hawala. Third, the pillars of the Hawala according to the jurists. Fourth, the terms of the Hawala. Fifth, various types of Hawalas. Sixth, the end of the Hawala/ faskh contract. Seventh, Hawala products.
- (b) The Hawala is said to be valid if it is executed on debt/in the form of money, not goods/concrete form.
- (c) It is permissible to transfer the debts of a deceased person to his heirs, even to other people.
- (d) The Hawala bil Ujrah contract is permissible, although some scholars prohibit this. The ulama allow it because they equate it with an ijarah contract ala Al-Asykhah (ijarah of services), so they are allowed to take wages for a service.
- (e) There are Hawalas that are prohibited, including: selling uncollectible debts and selling demand deposits (post-dated checks).
- (f) There are eleven fiqhiyyah rules in the Hawala. The first rule is that if someone transfers their debt to someone who is able to pay it, then they must accept the transfer of the debt. The second rule is that the actual purpose of the Hawala is to transfer rights. The third rule, anything that shows a transfer of debt, is called an agreement. Meanwhile, anything that shows satisfaction with the transfer is called qabul. The fourth rule, the origin of a contract is the consent of both parties (muhil and muhal). The fifth rule, the original law for canceling debt, is to pay it off in full. The sixth rule is that actually the debt in the Hawala does not require handover. The seventh rule, if the muhil transfers a debt to the muhal 'alaih, then does not accept it, so that the muhal 'alaih is in trouble, then the muhal is allowed to take back the Hawala. The eighth rule, if someone is unable to pay his debts, then he is not guilty of injustice. The ninth

rule, the Hawala does not end with the death of the muhal 'alaih. The tenth rule, the Hawala ends because it is fasakh and iqalah by the muhil and muhal lah. The eleventh rule, if the muhal lah dies, while the muhal 'alaih is the only heir, then the law of Hawala is not established for him.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Implementation of the Hawala in Society at Large (Advantages and Risks)

There are 3 studies on this topic. The approach and research methods used are: a qualitative approach with library research methods obtained from books and journals.

The research findings in this case are:

- (a) Faster, more efficient delivery times and great profit levels.
- (b) The use of this transaction is safer and more confidential because it is based on a high level of mutual trust between transaction actors.
- (c) This transaction fee is cheaper than banking services because currency differences do not undergo conversion.
- (d) The risks of implementing the Hawala agreement include: first, a decrease in banking profits throughout the world; second, a decrease in taxes received by a country's government; third, the country's monetary and fiscal policies are running ineffectively; fourth, it is difficult for the government to find out the circulation of foreign money in its country; fifth, there is no legal protection if a dispute occurs in Hawala transactions; and sixth, creating an increase in the potential for crime between countries.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Differences in Hawala Systems in Various Countries

There are 8 studies on this topic. The approach and research methods used are: a qualitative approach with library research methods obtained from books and journals. The research findings in this case are:

First, Majallah Al-Ahkam in Turkey. Majallah Al-Ahkam is a legal code used during the Ottoman Empire and applies in the territory that is now Turkey. Majallah Al-Ahkam is based on the teachings of the Hanafi school of thought, which is one of the four main schools of thought in Islamic fiqh. This code contains various provisions of Islamic civil law which cover various aspects of community life, including regulations related to the Hawala. In Majallah Al-Ahkam, there are differences in the division of Hawalas into three types, namely Hawala Muqayyadah, Hawala Muthlaqah, and Hawala Mubhamah. The following is a brief explanation of the three types of Hawala: (1) Hawala Muqayyadah: Hawala Muqayyadah is a type of Hawala which has certain conditions and limitations stipulated in the agreement. For example, the delivery of funds must be made within a specified time or to a specified party. If these conditions are not met, Hawala Muqayyadah can be declared null and void. (2) Hawala Muthlaqah: Hawala Muthlaqah is a type of Hawala that does not have certain conditions and limitations. In this Hawala, the party receiving the funds has the freedom to determine how and when to hand over the funds according to their needs. This provides more flexibility in the implementation of Hawala. (3) Hawala Mubhamah: Hawala Mubhamah is a type of Hawala that does not have clear provisions or explanations. In this Hawala, more specific provisions are not regulated in detail, and their implementation depends on

agreements or customs that apply in society. The Turkish government, adopting Majallah Al-Ahkam as the Islamic Civil Law Law in its legal system, has used this guideline in regulating the civil law applicable in the country.

Second, the practice of the Hawala agreement between Greece and Albania. The practice of Hawalas is a traditional and common money transfer system in the Muslim world. In this system, a money sender in the country of origin gives money to a Hawala agent or intermediary in the destination country. This intermediary then gives the money to the recipient in the destination country without going through international banking channels. However, please note that Greece and Albania are not Muslim-majority countries, and Hawala is not a commonly used money transfer method in either country. Generally, people in Greece and Albania will use international banking services such as Western Union or Eurogiro to send money abroad. If you say that banks in Greece charge lower fees for money transfer services to Albania than international money transfer services, such as Western Union and Eurogiro, then there could be other factors that influence the difference in fees. Perhaps banks in Greece have better relationships or networks with financial institutions in Albania, so they can offer lower costs when it comes to sending money to the country.

Third, the practice of the Hawala in the country of Djibouti. In the country of Djibouti, the practice of Hawalas plays an important role in money transfer transactions between countries. A Hawala is a form of financial contract that involves transferring debts or payment obligations from one party to another through an intermediary without involving physical money. In this context, Hawala is often used as an alternative to international money transfers in countries where the formal banking system is not very developed or is not accessible to everyone. One of the advantages of Hawala practice is its flexibility. This allows for fast and efficient money transfers without the need for complicated procedures or heavy bureaucracy. In this context, informal monetary practices using Hawala in Djibouti have worked in harmony with existing formal monetary policies. The presence of Hawala in Djibouti has several benefits for the real economic sector and social balance. Firstly, Hawala enables a smoother flow of funds between individuals and businesses, both at the national and international level. This can support economic growth by facilitating investment, trade and other business activities. Second, the practice of Hawala can help people who do not have access to the formal banking system or who lack trust in formal financial institutions. In this case, Hawala can provide safe and easily accessible financial services for those who need them, thereby increasing financial inclusion and social balance. However, it is important to remember that Hawala practices can also pose risks related to money laundering and terrorism financing if not properly regulated. Therefore, it is important for the government of Djibouti to ensure there is an adequate regulatory framework to monitor and supervise Hawala practices, so that they can operate safely and in accordance with the country's monetary and financial policies. In the end, harmonization between informal monetary practices using Hawala and formal monetary policy in the country of Djibouti has brought benefits to the real economic sector and social balance. However, it is also important to continue to pay attention to appropriate supervision and regulation to mitigate the risks that may arise from Hawala practices.

Fourth, the practice of Hawalas in Malaysia, Somalia and Afghanistan is widely used for money laundering and acts of terrorism. The practice of the Hawala is a money transfer system that is widely used in countries with a

majority Muslim population. This system is based on the principles of trust and family networks, where individuals or groups can transfer money or value quickly and efficiently without involving formal financial institutions. Although the practice of Hawala has legitimate uses, such as facilitating money transfers between family members living in different countries, financing education or helping in emergency financial situations, unfortunately it has also been misused for money laundering and acts of terrorism in several countries, including Malaysia, Somalia, and Afghanistan. Money laundering is the process of converting money resulting from illegal activities into assets that appear legally legitimate. Hawala practices can be used to facilitate money laundering by transferring funds anonymously and across national borders without too much oversight. This makes it attractive to those who want to hide the origin of their illegal funds. Apart from money laundering, Hawala practices can also be exploited by terrorist groups to finance their activities. Hawala's extensive network and lack of strict oversight make it a popular method for sending funds to individuals or terrorist groups in various countries. Governments in Malaysia, Somalia, and Afghanistan have recognized this risk and taken steps to combat money laundering and acts of terrorism involving Hawala practices. They have increased cooperation with international financial institutions, strengthened regulations related to financial transparency, and increased monitoring and law enforcement against suspect Hawala practices. It is important to note that although the practice of Hawala can be abused, the majority of its use is legal and legitimate. Many people use this system to transfer money quickly and easily, especially in countries with limited financial infrastructure. Action against abused practices should be focused on the individual or group abusing the system, not on the entire practice of Hawala as a whole.

Fifth, management, risk control and the government's role in the Hawala funds transfer network in the Gulf countries, such as: Qatar, the United Arab Emirates and Kuwait. In Gulf countries such as Qatar, the United Arab Emirates and Kuwait, the management and control of risks related to the Hawalaed funds transfer network is usually regulated by local financial authorities and governments. Hawala is a traditional, non-banking system used to transfer money between individuals or groups without involving formal financial institutions. The government has an important role in regulating and supervising Hawala activities to ensure compliance with the law, prevent money laundering practices, and protect national interests. The following are several aspects that need to be considered in management, risk control, and the government's role in the Hawalaed fund transfer network in the Gulf countries:

- (1) Regulations and Policies: The government issues regulations and policies to regulate Hawala operations, including registration requirements, licensing, and compliance with security standards. The aim is to prevent the use of the Hawala network for illegal purposes such as financing terrorism or money laundering.
- (2) Registration and Licensing: The government requires Hawala service providers to register and obtain an official license. This allows financial authorities to monitor, evaluate and audit Hawala's activities on a regular basis.
- (3) Transaction Reporting: Hawala service providers are usually required to report certain transactions to financial authorities, especially if there are indications of suspicious or unlawful activity. This reporting helps the government track and prevent illegal activities.
- (4) Sanctions and Punishments: The government has the power to impose sanctions and penalties on Hawala service providers who violate established regulations and policies. This includes license revocation, fines, or other legal action in accordance with applicable law.

(5) International Cooperation: Gulf countries generally cooperate with other countries in combating cross-border financial crimes, including through information exchange and law enforcement coordination. This collaboration is important in controlling the risk that Hawala's funds transfer network can be used for illegal purposes.

Sixth, the development of initial H contracts in sharia financial institutions in Indonesia has experienced significant progress in the last few years. The following are several developments related to Hawalas in sharia financial institutions in Indonesia: (1) Supporting Regulations: The Financial Services Authority (OJK) in Indonesia has issued various regulations that support the use of Hawalas in sharia financial institutions. This includes operational guidelines, regulations regarding public offerings of sukuk, and regulations governing aspects of sharia contracts and products in general. This regulation provides a clear framework for sharia financial institutions to use Hawalas. (2) Use in Investment Products: Islamic financial institutions in Indonesia are increasingly using Hawalas in their investment products. For example, in sharia mutual fund products, customers can give wakalah to investment managers to manage and invest their funds in accordance with sharia principles. Hawalas are also used in term savings products and sharia term deposits. (3) Product Innovation: In an effort to meet customer needs, sharia financial institutions continue to develop new products based on Hawalas. For example, they offer wakalah-based investment products that focus on specific sectors, such as property, renewable energy, or the infrastructure sector. This provides an opportunity for customers to invest according to their preferences while still complying with sharia principles. (4) Public Awareness: The development of sharia financial institutions in Indonesia has also increased public awareness about Hawalas. More and more people are choosing to use sharia-based financial products and services, including Hawalas. This encourages sharia financial institutions to continue to develop products and services that suit customer needs.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Hawala agreement on Islamic Financial Inclusion during the period 2010 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there were 32 published journal articles. Second, based on Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer bibliometric studies, the results of network visualization around the Hawala agreement on Islamic Financial Inclusion are divided into 3 clusters and 46 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 24 topics, cluster 2 consists of 16 topics, and cluster 3 consists of 6 topics. Third, based on Mapping Research Topics using library research studies, there are 10 topics related to the Hawala agreement on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application of the Hawala Agreement in the Crime of Terrorism, Money Laundering and Abuse in Other Crimes; (2) Implementation of the Hawala Agreement in Islamic Financial Inclusion; (3) Application of the Hawala Agreement in Problem Financing; (4) Implementation of the Take Over Transaction Agreement; (5) Implementation of the Hawala Agreement in Multiservice Financing; (6) Juridical Study of the Hawala Agreement; (7) Hawala according to the Koran and Hadith; (8) Hawala Agreement according to Muamalah Fiqh and Fiqhiyyah Rules; (9) Implementation of the Hawala Agreement in Society at Large

(Advantages and Risks); and (10) Differences in Hawala systems in various countries.

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